

PHOENIX

The Rise of Citizens Voices
for a Greener Europe

Participation in **H**olistic **EN**vironmental/Ecological **I**nnovations

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER: 101037328

Guidelines for the implementation of TCCD co-design evaluation

Task 5.2. Participatory testing, localisation and optimisation of the
evaluation plan

WP5. Evaluation and Impact Assessment

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Introduction

This document aims at describing all the guidelines for the implementation of the TCCD co-design evaluation systems that Local Partners are asked to undertake in order to support task 5.2., particularly, the elaboration of deliverable 5.4. As indicated in the Grant Agreement, task 5.2 aims to create a citizen's science process to assist PHOENIX with finalising the impact evaluation framework. This co-evaluation process will consider the pilots' context and, therefore, tailor design a module for impact evaluation that is specific to the local conditions and the specific process which they will implement. The data collected and generated by Task 5.2 will contribute to updating the evaluation plan and optimising the impact evaluation instruments.

These guidelines will cover qualitative data to be collected through 5 different instruments interconnected but with different objectives that will be detailed in the following sections: (1) qualitative case study description, (2) TCCD internal evaluation session, (3) TCCD qualitative survey, (4) cross-TCCD online focus group and (5) TCCD impact stories.

Local partners, both academics and practitioners depending on their proximity to the pilots, will be asked to:

1. gather information through qualitative desk research concerning the case-study (and elaborate an English report);
2. carry out the TCCD internal evaluation session (to be run, recorded, transcribed and translated);
3. carry out the TCCD qualitative survey (implement the survey - a link will be sent - and translate the open answers);
4. support the cross-TCCD online focus group (through the selection of 1 or 2 TCCD representatives);
5. support the impact stories collection.

The following chapters intend to specify, explain, and support the local partners' activities in relation to the TCCD evaluation.

At the end of the document you can find the following appendices that should be used to data collection: (1) the Participant identification template to collect information about the TCCD participants, (2) the case-study template and (3) the TCCD qualitative survey questions.

DEADLINES

Considering the current project timeline, which plans to deliver Deliverable 5.4 on M24, it is necessary to complete all data collection and deliver the reports by mid-autumn, ideally by November 30th (please note that this deadline does not account for the online cross-TCCD focus group).

Considering the previous one-to-one meetings with all Local Partners, it is important to be aware that for the evaluation team it is really useful to receive the data as soon as possible. There is no need to wait for the completion of data collection for all instruments/steps – You can send it to us as soon as you complete each step of the data collection.

Translation of the TCCD survey: the translation into local languages of the survey must be sent to us (UC and SOTON) by June 30th, so that we can insert it in a link that will be made available to you.

1. Qualitative case study description

Objectives: the qualitative case study description aims to provide in-depth and nuanced insights into different forms and processes that TCCDs can experience. These case studies aim to document and analyse the successes, challenges, and outcomes of these initiatives, as well as the processes and mechanisms used to engage the participants. The information gathered will be useful to create a shared knowledge base that can identify best practices by analysing the successes and challenges of different initiatives to be applied to other contexts.

Instructions: The case studies description (ranging from 500 to 1000 words) should be organised as follow – please use the template available in the appendix A:

Part 1 – TCCD identification and local conditions

- 1. Identification:** The identification of the case study is usually brief and descriptive, with the pilot name, region, local partners involved, green deal policy area, type of democratic innovation and participants characterisation;
- 2. Overview:** The overview provides a brief summary of the initiative, including its goals, methods, and outcomes.
- 3. Context:** The context section provides information on the political, social, and economic context in which the initiative was developed.

Part 2 – The process

- 4. Methods:** The methods section describes the specific methods and techniques used to engage citizens in the decision-making process, such as public hearings, town hall meetings, citizen juries, or online forums, as well as the participants recruitment criteria. This section may also describe any tools or technologies used to support the process and the number of meetings.

Part 3 – Impacts and lessons learned

- 5. Outcomes:** The outcomes section describes the results and impact of the initiative, including any changes in policy, decision-making processes, or community dynamics that resulted from the initiative. This section may also describe any unintended consequences or challenges encountered during implementation.
- 6. Analysis:** The analysis section provides a critical reflection on the initiative, drawing on insights and lessons learned from the case study. This section may include a discussion of the strengths and weaknesses of the initiative, as well as recommendations for future practice and research.

2. TCCD Qualitative Survey

IMPORTANT – THIS TCCD QUALITATIVE SURVEY MUST BE APPLIED BEFORE THE INTERNAL EVALUATION SESSION AND THE ONLINE CROSS PILOTS FOCUS GROUP

Objectives: This TCCD qualitative survey to be implemented during a TCCD session, and transcribed (only open answers) and translated by the local partners, aims to gather TCCD participants individual opinions and reflections on their participation.

This individual self-reflection moment will help us to gather information on how to improve the TCCD co-design process. Therefore, participants experiences and insights are critical in this update process by:

- Share insights and personal experience about the co-design process;
- Reflect on their own role and contributions to the co-design process;
- Identify areas for improvement in their own performance and contributions considering the SWOT analysis components – Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats.

Instructions:

- 1. Structure:** the survey is divided in five parts with 26 questions in total ([Appendix C](#)): Part A is dedicated to the co-design process; Part B is focused on the TCCD; Part C on the co-design satisfaction and expectations; Part D aims to explore the relation between the TCCD and the future; Part E is dedicated to the sociodemographic information;
- 2. Duration:** the average time to complete the questionnaire is 30 minutes;
- 3. Application:** a link to the survey will be provided and should be applied to all TCCD participants – Local partners may be asked to assist with the translation of the survey. Although we prefer the online survey, if local partners face challenges with its implementation, they can print it and fill it out offline. In this case, the completed surveys should then be scanned and uploaded to Qualtrics.
- 4. After application:** once the data collection is completed, local partners are asked to translate the responses – only those concerning open questions - to English and provide them to the TCCD evaluation team WP 5.

Important Note: This survey should be applied also to those participants that drop out (if any) during this process to understand their reasons.

3. TCCD Internal evaluation session

IMPORTANT: THIS TCCD EVALUATION SESSION IS MANAGED BY THE LOCAL PARTNERS
- Local Partners will decide if they need to translate this document to the moderators or not.

Before the discussion

- 1. Participants selection:** the number of participants selected from the TCCD to take part in the internal evaluation session should have a **minimum of 12 and a maximum of 15**. This decision is internal and shared with the TCCD participants but should ensure the diversity and plurality of actors concerning age, gender, nationality and social group – use the appendix B to fill with the participants information. The TCCD implementers may decide whether this is an activity embedded in other activities of the TCCD or a separate one.
- 1. Informed consent** – participants should sign an informed consent before the session start – see Appendix D. Since this session will **be translated, a recording equipment should be used and participants should be asked for permission, ensuring that the names of the participants are anonymised**;
- 2. Facilitator/Moderator:** the facilitator and moderator should be the TCCD implementer or someone familiarized with group discussion;
- 3. Duration:** between one hour and half and two hours (1h30m to 2h00m);
- 4. Space planning:** This moment of self-reflection should occur in a safe and supportive environment for participants to share their experiences and feedback. Since this session will **be translated, a recording equipment should be used and participants should be asked for permission, ensuring that the names of the participants are anonymised**
- 5. Ensure everyone has a chance to speak:** Make sure everyone has a chance to speak and share their thoughts. Avoid allowing any one participant to dominate the conversation;
- 6. Monitor the discussion:** make sure that you (facilitator) pay attention to what participants are saying and respond with follow-up questions or comments that encourage further discussion. It is also important to make sure the discussion stays on track and focused on the topics outlined.

During the discussion

- 7. Welcome:** By welcoming the group to the discussion on the self-evaluation activity of the co-design process, the facilitator should inform the objectives to the participants:

Objective	The objective of this internal evaluation session is to analyse participants' experience and self-reflection on the TCCD co-design process.
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By encouraging the discussion and reminding the participants to be respectful and constructive in their feedback, the facilitator should now explain that considering this main objective, the discussion will consider the following aspects (please introduce each of the following questions one at the time - please note that the time management must be done according to the dynamics of the group; some questions may generate more discussion and others less. This management must be considered by each facilitator):

GUIDING QUESTIONS	Adequacy of the composition of the TCCD and its diversity in relation to the socio-cultural specificities of the territory: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Do you feel that the TCCD composition reflects the sociocultural diversity of your territorial context?</i> - <i>Does it address the primary socio-environmental problems?</i>
	Perception of the collective management of the co-design process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Were your opinions heard and acted upon during the co-design process?</i>
	Perception about their participation (or not) in the implementation of activities, strategies and choice of tools for codesign: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Were you given sufficient support to participate in the activities?</i> - <i>Which activities did you enjoy?</i> - <i>Which did you not enjoy? Why?</i>
	Results – successful definition of TCCD or not: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Were you satisfied with the results of the co-design process?</i> - <i>What areas for improvement did you identify?</i>

After the discussion

- 8. Closing:** The facilitator should summarize the key insights and learnings from the internal evaluation session (in a table, for example), and ask participants to confirm whether they agree with the information collected or if they want to make any changes:

Closing questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Does anyone want to add or change anything?- Do you think these ideas convey what has been discussed here?
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- 9. Transcribe and translate to English the Internal Evaluation Session** using the questions to structure the document, alongside with the Internal Evaluation Session Participant Identification Form; During the transcript, to ensure anonymisation, there is no need to identify participants by name. Instead, Local Partners may assign each participant an alphabetic letter, for example.

4. Cross-TCCD online focus-group

IMPORTANT: THIS FOCUS GROUP IS MANAGED BY THE EVALUATION TEAM – UNIVERSITY OF COIMBRA AND SOTON

Note: All participants should fill the Participant Identification Form (Appendix B)

Before the discussion

- 1. Participants selection:** Each TCCD should select 1 (**one**) **internal representative** who will reflect on the overall process in a knowledge exchange moment – internally selected by TCCD participants who can best represent the diversity of positions and interests within the involved groups. While it is recommended that the selection process consider the **ability to speak English, this is not mandatory**. If necessary, solutions can be discussed to address language barriers, such as finding someone to translate the representative's speech. Informed consent – participants should sign an informed consent before the session start – see appendix E.
- 2. Facilitator/Moderator:** the facilitators and moderators will be two/three members of UC and SOTON teams;
- 3. Duration: one hour and half** between one hour and half and two hours (up to 3 hours maximum);
- 4. Space planning:** This moment of self-reflection should occur in a safe and supportive environment for participants to share their experiences and feedback. A slide will be shared with all participants during the discussion to help them follow the evolution of the debate and the information being collected - this will facilitate the identification of possible misunderstandings due to language barriers. This session will **be recorded to facilitate transcription and analysis and participants should be asked for permission, ensuring that the names of the participants are anonymised**; Informed consent – participants should sign an informed consent before the session start – see Appendix E.
- 5. Ensure everyone has a chance to speak:** Make sure everyone has a chance to speak and share their thoughts. Avoid allowing any one participant to dominate the conversation;
- 6. Monitor the discussion:** make sure that the facilitators are paying attention to what participants are saying and respond with follow-up questions or comments that encourage further discussion. It is also important to make sure the discussion stays on track and focused on the topics outlined.

7. Exchange moment between TCCD representatives: before the discussion there will be a round of presentations on the TCCD representatives.

During the discussion

8. Welcome: By welcoming the group to the discussion on the self-evaluation activity of the co-design process, the facilitator should inform the objectives to the participants (please introduce each of the following questions one at the time - please note that the time management must be done according to the dynamics of the group; some questions may generate more discussion and others less. This management must be considered by each facilitator):

Objective	The objective of this focus group is to identify the main strengths, weaknesses, threats and opportunities of the TCCD co-design process through participants' experiences, and based on this, develop a set of recommendations for the TCCD co-evaluation process to update the modular evaluation plan.
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By encouraging the discussion and reminding the participants to be respectful and constructive in their feedback, the facilitator should now explain that considering this main objective, he/she will present – in a shared slide - a set of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats identified during the self-reflection moment (qualitative survey) and will ask them to check if those are suitable or if they want to reconsider their initial choices and move forward to other dimensions of the collective reflection:

GUIDING QUESTIONS	The facilitator shows the strengths identified and asks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>With regard to these strengths identified during the self-reflection moment by TCCD participants, what do you think, is there anything you want to remove or add?</i>
	The facilitator shows the weaknesses identified and asks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>With regard to these weaknesses identified during the self-reflection moment by TCCD participants, what do you think, is there anything you want to remove or add?</i>

	<p>The facilitator shows the opportunities identified and asks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>With regard to these opportunities identified during the self-reflection moment by TCCD participants, what do you think? Is there anything you want to remove or add?</i>
	<p>The facilitator shows the threats identified and ask</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>With regard to these threats identified during the self-reflection moment by TCCD participants, what do you think? Is there anything you want to remove or add?</i>

After the discussion

- 9. Closing:** Two moments: 1) The facilitator should present the SWOT analysis co-created with the participants and ask them to confirm whether they agree with the information collected or if they want to make any changes; 2) based on this, the group is invited to develop a set of recommendations for the TCCD co-evaluation process;

<p>Closing questions</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) This SWOT analysis is the result of our discussion. Please take a look at it and: <i>Does it reflect your experiences and ideas exchanged during this session? Do you want to add anything?</i> 2) <i>Based on the SWOT analysis, we suggest you can contribute to identify a set of recommendations for the TCCD co-evaluation process: recommendation 1; recommendation 2... etc</i>
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- 10. Produce the report:** Document the findings based on your notes and on the session recording of the focus group in a written report alongside with the Focus Group Participant Identification Form. During the transcript, to ensure anonymisation, there is no need to identify participants by name. Instead, to each participant an alphabetic letter will be assigned.

5. Letter of support – (Up to 6 months after the internal evaluation session)

Objectives: The Letter of support – follow up - aims to capture the impact of TCCD co-design process on the life of a participant.

Instructions

- 1. Deadline:** The Letter of support should be collected 6 months after the co-design process;
- 2. Applicability:** the analysis of the letters of support will be included in the *D5.7: Pilot Evaluation and it will be used in communication;*
- 3. Structure:** the letter of support should be a written document in the participant language, transcribed to English by the Local Partner, that narrates the impact of the TCCD co-design process at a personal level. An example will be provided to each Local Partner. As an option, the letter of support can be accompanied by a short-filmed testimony of the impact of TCCD participation (this is optional) which will be analysed only by the evaluators to recognise the participant's point of view.
- 4. Who should be asked to write:** 1 or 2 participants of the TCCD co-design process identified by the Local Partners;

Appendices:

A. Template for case-study description – if you have doubts about how to write the case study, please visit Participedia's that provide similar examples (<https://participedia.net/search?selectedCategory=case>)

PART 1

1. [TCCD IDENTIFICATION – PILOT NAME AND REGION]

2. [NAME OF PARTNER IN CHARGE OF THE TCCD]

3. [GREEN DEAL POLICY AREA]

4. [TYPE OF DEMOCRATIC INNOVATION]

5. [PARTICIPANTS COMPOSITION: AGE, GENDER, EDUCATION, NATIONALITY, STAKEHOLDER CATEGORY: Citizen, Practitioners (urban planners, architects, environmental experts, among others), Decision-makers, Activists, Social/environmental movements, NGOs, Business people, socio-environmental vulnerable groups, nature (non-humans) representative, representative of future generations, representative of minorities and migrants, representative of women, scientific community member, other - please specify]

IDENTIFICATION AND LOCAL CONDITIONS

6. [OVERVIEW]

[The overview provides a brief summary of the initiative, including its goals, methods, and outcomes.]

7. [CONTEXT]

[The context section provides information on the political, social, and economic context in which the initiative was developed.]

PART 2

THE PROCESS

8. [METHODS]

[The methods section describes the specific methods and techniques used to engage citizens in the decision-making process, such as public hearings, town hall meetings, citizen juries, or online forums, and the participants recruitment criteria. This section may also

describe any tools or technologies used to support the process and the number of meetings.]

PART 3

IMPACTS AND LESSONS LEARNED

9. [OUTCOMES]

[The outcomes section describes the results and impact of the initiative, including any changes in policy, decision-making processes, or community dynamics that resulted from the initiative. This section may also describe any unintended consequences or challenges encountered during implementation.]

10. [ANALYSIS]

[The analysis section provides a critical reflection on the initiative, drawing on insights and lessons learned from the case study. This section may include a discussion of the strengths and weaknesses of the initiative, as well as recommendations for future practice and research.]

[You are welcome to include pictures or any other supporting information you think is relevant, considering the data protection regulations]

11. REFERENCES [OPTIONAL]

PART 4

12. CONTACT INFORMATION

[NAME/S OF THE PERSON/S RESPONSIBLE FOR THE PREPARATION OF THIS CASE STUDY]

[IDENTIFICATION OF THE PARTNER/S INVOLVED]

[DATE AND LOCAL, REGION]

B. TCCD Internal Evaluation Session - Participant Identification Form

1. Age: _____

2. Gender:

Female [1]

Male [2]

Other/s [3]. Please, specify: _____

Prefer not to say [4]

3. Occupation: _____

4. Are you a resident of the area where the session will be conducted?

Yes [1]

No [2]

4.1. If “No”, please indicate where you reside: _____

5. Nationality: _____

6. Do you have a university degree?

Yes [1]

No [2]

6.1. If yes, can you please tell us the field of study: _____

7. How many years did you study? _____

8. Have you participated in an evaluation session (or focus group) before?

Yes [1]

No [2]

8.1. If “Yes”, how many times have you participated in an evaluation session (or focus group)? _____

9. Which category do you most fall into?

Citizen [1]

Practitioners (urban planners, architects, environmental experts. among others) [2]

Decision-makers [3]

Activists, Social/environmental movements [4]

NGOs [5]

Business people [6]

Other [7]. Please specify: _____

10. Are you representing the interests of someone, something, some cause or some specific group?

Yes [1]

No [2]

10.1. If “Yes”, please specify who/what: _____

Thank you for taking the time to complete this form. Your information will be kept confidential and will only be used for the purpose of identifying the participants for the evaluation session.

C. TCCD qualitative survey

You are invited to participate in the project PHOENIX – The rise of citizens’ voice for a green Europe. PHOENIX is a 42-month research and innovation action funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme, Grant Agreement n° 101037328. It began in February 2022 and will come to end in July 2025 (more information about the project and to help you decide whether you would like to participate in PHOENIX project activities can be found at https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ig3KtnR0eTZL_F819_FZJfE11c07jcEE/edit?usp=sharing&oid=105039828406974423400&rtopof=true&sd=true. It is developed within an international consortium, coordinated by the Centre for Social Studies, at the University of Coimbra. PHOENIX Principal Investigator is Giovanni Allegretti.

This survey aims to gather your opinions and reflections on your participation in the Territorial Commission for Co-Design (TCCD). Completing this survey is completely voluntary, we will not record your name, and the survey will be coded to ensure the anonymity of answers. All personal information you provide will be kept confidential, anonymous, and treated in accordance with the EU regulations on personal data protection. Your decision whether to participate or not will not affect your current or future relationship with the researchers or anyone else involved in the PHOENIX project. You can stop the questionnaire at any time and refuse to answer any questions you do not wish to answer. If you decide to participate in this survey but later change your mind, you can request to withdraw your survey transcript from the study by contacting the researcher responsible (contact information at the end of this information).

We value your participation in our research and are committed to ensuring transparency and effective communication throughout the entire process. You now have the opportunity to authorize us to contact you via email during and after your participation, even if you decide to drop out of the study. This will enable us to gather valuable feedback and evaluate the co-design process more comprehensively. By choosing to leave your email address and authorizing us to contact you, you agree to the following: We will only contact you regarding matters directly related to the research study you participated in. This includes seeking feedback, addressing any concerns or questions you may have, and informing you of any relevant updates or findings.

By providing your consent, you are agreeing to allow us to collect personal information about you for the purpose of this study.

We thank you in advance for your cooperation. Your participation is very important for us!

If you have any questions, you can address them to Fátima Alves (fatimaa@uab.pt) and Diogo Guedes Vidal (diogo.vidal@uc.pt), from Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People & the Planet (CFE), University of Coimbra, Portugal.

Informed consent:

I agree to participate in the research study. I understand the purpose and nature of this study and I am participating voluntarily. I understand that I can withdraw from the study at any time, without any penalty or consequences.

Yes

I agree to authorise the project to contact me via email during and after my participation, even if I decide to drop out of the study to give feedback and evaluate the co-design process more comprehensively.

Yes

No

If yes, please leave your email here: _____

PART A

The CO-DESIGN

1. What is co-design for you?

2. Was this your first time participating in a co-design process?

Yes [1]

No [2]

3. Can you share with us some words that translate your experience in this co-design process?

3.1. From your description of this co-design experience, can you please identify which are:

A. The main strengths: _____

B. The main weaknesses: _____

C. The main opportunities: _____

D. The main threats: _____

PART B

The Territorial Commission for Co-Design (TCCD)

4. Could you please briefly explain what the Territorial Commission for Co-design is? _____

5. Do you consider that the objectives of the TCCD were clear and well-defined?

Yes [1]

No [2]

5.1. Is it possible to identify some of the objectives of the TCCD? _____

6. How did you feel about the composition of the TCCD in terms of the diversity of participants and stakeholders involved?

Not diverse enough [1]

Somewhat diverse [2]

Moderately diverse [3]

Very diverse [4]

Don't know/Can't answer [5]

6.1. Did you feel that any individual or group was missing from the TCCD's composition, in light of the socio-environmental problems of your territorial context?

Yes [1]

No [2]

I don't know [3]

6.1.1. If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, please identify who was missing from the TCCD's composition and explain why their presence would have been important. _____

6.2. Did the TCCD include a representative of future generations?

Yes [1]

No [2]

I don't know [3]

6.2.1. If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, can you please explain the main

contribution of this integration to the group discussion?

6.3. Did the TCCD include a representative of nature (non-human)?

- Yes [1]
- No [2]
- I don't know [3]

6.3.1. If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, can you please explain the main contribution of this integration to the group discussion?

6.3.2. In your opinion, how to consider nature and non-human species interests in the co-design process? _____

6.3.3. What challenges do you anticipate in incorporating non-human perspectives in co-design processes? _____

6.3.4. Do you anticipate any ethical considerations that should be considered when incorporating non-human perspectives in co-design processes? Can you please justify?

PART C

SATISFACTION AND EXPECTATIONS

7. How satisfied were you with the activities and tools used during the co-design process?

- Very unsatisfied [1]
- Somewhat unsatisfied [2]
- Neutral [3]
- Somewhat satisfied [4]
- Very satisfied [5]
- Don't know/Can't answer [6]

7.1. Could you please justify your previous answer?

8. What were your initial expectations regarding your involvement in this co-design process?

9. Concerning your initial expectations, do you consider that the TCCD:

- Met my expectations [1]
- Exceeded my expectations [2]
- Partially met my expectations [3]
- Did not meet my expectations [4]
- I had no expectations [5]

10. Did you feel that your opinions and feedback were considered during the co-design process?

- Yes [1]
- No [2]
- Don't know/Can't answer [3]

10.1. If you answered "No" to the previous question, could you please explain how you felt and the possible reasons why your opinions and feedback weren't considered during the co-design process?

10.2. Did you participate in all meetings?

- Yes [1]
- No [2]
- I don't know / Prefer not to say [3]

10.3. Have you ever entertained the idea of embarking on a different creative journey and parting ways with this TCCD co-design process?

- Frequently - I often contemplate exploring alternative avenues of creativity [1]
- Occasionally - I occasionally ponder the possibility of pursuing different collaborative endeavours [2]
- Rarely - I am committed to this co-design process and seldom consider quitting. [3]
- Never - I am fully devoted to the co-design process and have no intentions of quitting [4]

11. Do you consider that participating in this co-design processes and the commitment in this participation would be worthy of monetary compensation?

- Money plays no role, my motivation lies in the experience itself [1]
- Monetary compensation would be a nice bonus, but not a crucial factor [2]
- My participation and commitment would be greater if there is a significant financial reward involved [3]

Considering the time-consuming nature of this co-design process, in future I will only participate if there is monetary compensation. [4]

12. Do you consider that the participation in these co-design processes could greatly benefit from providing support to participants in the following areas, as needed:

- Recognizing the importance of reliable childcare arrangements to enable participants, particularly women, to fully engage in the co-design process without concerns about their children's well-being [1]
- Offering flexibility in work schedules or remote work options to help participants effectively manage family affairs while actively participating in the co-design process [2]
- Implementing measures to mitigate potential job loss or negative impacts on participants' careers [3]
- Providing financial assistance or compensation to address any income loss or financial implications that participants may experience while dedicating their time and energy to the co-design process [4]
- Other. Please specify [5]

13. Would you participate in a similar co-design process in the future?

- Yes [1]
- No [2]
- Don't know/Can't answer [3]

14. In your opinion can this particular co-design process be applied in other contexts in the future?

- Yes [1]
- No [2]
- Don't know/Can't answer [3]

14.1 - If you answered "no" to the previous question, could you please specify why?

15. Did your participation in the TCCD have any impact on you or your community, whether positive or negative?

- Yes [1]
- No [2]
- Don't know/Can't answer [3]

15.1. If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, could you please describe the type of impact? _____

16. What could have been done differently to improve the co-design process? _____

PART D

TCCD AND THE FUTURE

17. Imagine you are in 2050. Looking back at the ecological transition that has taken place, we would like to understand the role that previous generations played in shaping the future we live in today (2050). As a member of the future generation, please reflect on the actions and contributions of the present generations (up to 2023) towards the ecological transition. In your opinion, what specific actions and roles did the present generations (2023) play in the transition to a more equitable and environmentally conscious society?

18. In your opinion, how can TCCDs contribute to fostering an ecological transition that encompasses all regions and ensures inclusivity without leaving anyone behind?

18.1. What is missing for this purpose to become a reality?

19. Do you have any additional comments or feedback about the TCCD or the co-design process?

PART E

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

20. What is your gender?

Female [1]

Male [2]

Other/s [3]. Please, specify: _____

Prefer not to say [4]

21. What year were you born (yyyy)? _____

22. What is your nationality? _____

23. Do you have a university degree?

Yes [1]

No [2]

23.1. If yes, can you please tell us the field of study: _____

24. How many years did you study? _____

25. Which of the following categories do you fall in the most?

Citizen [1]

Practitioners [2]

Decision-makers [3]

Phoenix partners [4]

Experts [5]

Activists [6]

NGOs representative [7]

Social/environmental movements [8]

Business people [9]

Other [10]: _____

26. Please, describe as objectively as possible your occupation or, in the case of being unemployed, the last one performed:

D. Informed consent for the TCCD internal evaluation session

This study is part of the PHOENIX project, a consortium coordinated by Centre for Social Studies (CES) of the University of Coimbra, Portugal, and formed by: Fondazione Giangiacomo Feltrinelli (FGF, Italy), University of Florence (UNIFI, Italy), Res Publica (France), French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS, France), The Good Lobby (TGL, Belgium), Instituto de Políticas y Bienes Públicos (CSIC, Spain), University of Southampton (SOUTHAMPTON, United Kingdom), University of Szeged (USZ, Hungary), University of Groningen (RUG, Netherlands), e-Governance Academy (eGA, Estonia), Associação Oficina de Planeamento e Participação (OFICINA, Portugal), ONESOURCE (Portugal), University of Coimbra (UC, Portugal), University of Iceland (UoI, Iceland). It is funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme, Grant Agreement nº 101037328 and started on February 2022 and ends in July 2025.

The purpose of the study is enriching Democratic Innovations for Green Deal pathway for which interviews will help understand the local territorial, social, cultural, and political context of pilots' territories for PHOENIX project. It is coordinated by **Fátima Alves** (fatimaa@uab.pt), who you can contact if you wish to clarify doubts or share comments.

Your participation in the study consists of participating in an TCCD internal evaluation session that is expected to take no longer than 1 hour and 30 minutes and has no expected associated risks.

If you agree, your participation will be recorded in video and audio format. If you allow it, the recording will remain accessible exclusively to the team for transcription and subsequent analysis of information. If you agree, this register may also include research dissemination materials, accessible to a wider audience through (project website, social media, archives, etc.). This disclosure may be made anonymously or with disclosure of your identity, according to your wishes.

Participation is voluntary and you can withdraw from the study at any time, without having to provide any justification. The collected data will be stored securely in researchers' professional device protected, password-protected during the research and removed at the end of the project. From this moment to the next five years, the data will be stored on a server or a specific device intended for this purpose at CES. When necessary, the transference of sensitive and personal data to other project partners involved in the work, researchers will exclusively use the project platform, which offers different provisions for security against unauthorised access.

You have the right to access the registration of your participation at any time, by contacting the CES Data Protection Officer (epd@ces.uc.pt) or the [partner short name] data protection officer [name and email]

This informed consent is necessary to ensure that you understand the purpose and conditions of your participation in the study.

	Yes	No	N.A.
1. I declare that the objectives of the study and the conditions of my participation have been clearly explained and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about them.			
2. I authorize my participation to be recorded in audio format (voice).			
3. I authorize my participation to be recorded in video (image) format.			
4. I authorize my identity to be revealed.			
5. I authorize the use of my email address and phone number for internal communication			
6. I would like to receive an unedited digital copy of my entry.			
7. I agree to participate in this study, under the conditions described above.			
8. In case I withdraw, I agree to be contacted to fill out a survey in case			

Any participant in this study may change the conditions for granting the use of the sound and/or image recording, if he/she so wishes, and must request it in writing to the project coordinator.

<p>Name and signature of participant</p> <p>Name:.....</p> <p>Date:</p> <p>Contacts:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>Signature:</p>	<p>Name and signature of the researcher</p> <p>Name:.....</p> <p>Date:</p> <p>Contacts:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>Signature:.....</p>
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E. Informed consent for the cross-TCCD online focus group

This study is part of the PHOENIX project, a consortium coordinated by Centre for Social Studies (CES) of the University of Coimbra, Portugal, and formed by: Fondazione Giangiacomo Feltrinelli (FGF, Italy), University of Florence (UNIFI, Italy), Res Publica (France), French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS, France), The Good Lobby (TGL, Belgium), Instituto de Políticas y Bienes Públicos (CSIC, Spain), University of Southampton (SOUTHAMPTON, United Kingdom), University of Szeged (USZ, Hungary), University of Groningen (RUG, Netherlands), e-Governance Academy (eGA, Estonia), Associação Oficina de Planeamento e Participação (OFICINA, Portugal), ONESOURCE (Portugal), University of Coimbra (UC, Portugal), University of Iceland (UoI, Iceland). It is funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme, Grant Agreement nº 101037328 and started on February 2022 and ends in July 2025.

The purpose of the study is enriching Democratic Innovations for Green Deal pathway for which interviews will help understand the local territorial, social, cultural, and political context of pilots' territories for PHOENIX project. It is coordinated by **Fátima Alves** (fatimaa@uab.pt), who you can contact if you wish to clarify doubts or share comments.

Your participation in the study consists of participating in a cross-TCCD online focus group that is expected to take no longer than 1 hour and 30 minutes and has no expected associated risks.

If you agree, your participation will be recorded in video and audio format. If you allow it, the recording will remain accessible exclusively to the team for transcription and subsequent analysis of information. If you agree, this register may also include research dissemination materials, accessible to a wider audience through (project website, social media, archives, etc.). This disclosure may be made anonymously or with disclosure of your identity, according to your wishes.

Participation is voluntary and you can withdraw from the study at any time, without having to provide any justification. The collected data will be stored securely in researchers' professional device protected, password-protected during the research and removed at the end of the project. From this moment to the next five years, the data will be stored on a server or a specific device intended for this purpose at CES. When necessary, the transference of sensitive and personal data to other project partners involved in the work, researchers will exclusively use the project platform, which offers different provisions for security against unauthorised access.

You have the right to access the registration of your participation at any time, by contacting the CES Data Protection Officer (epd@ces.uc.pt) or the **[partner short name]** data protection officer **[name and email]**

This informed consent is necessary to ensure that you understand the purpose and conditions of your participation in the study.

	Yes	No	N.A.
1. I declare that the objectives of the study and the conditions of my participation have been clearly explained and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about them.			
2. I authorize my participation to be recorded in audio format (voice).			
3. I authorize my participation to be recorded in video (image) format.			
4. I authorize my identity to be revealed.			
5. I authorize the use of my email address and phone number for internal communication			
6. I would like to receive an unedited digital copy of my entry.			
7. I agree to participate in this study, under the conditions described above.			
8. In case I withdraw, I agree to be contacted to fill out a survey in case			

Any participant in this study may change the conditions for granting the use of the sound and/or image recording, if he/she so wishes, and must request it in writing to the project coordinator.

<p>Name and signature of participant</p> <p>Name:.....</p> <p>Date:</p> <p>Contacts:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>Signature:</p>	<p>Name and signature of the researcher</p> <p>Name:.....</p> <p>Date:</p> <p>Contacts:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>Signature:.....</p>
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